

ISSUES OF THE FORMATION OF MORAL CULTURE IN POSTMODERN SOCIETY

Davronjon Ma'rufjonovich Khusanov

Instructor of Computer Science,

Fergana "Temurbeklar Maktabi" Military-Academic Lyceum

ORCID ID: 0009-0004-6998-3997

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Abstract: In the article, the theoretical foundations of the socio-philosophical research of the dialectic of the change of moral values in the postmodern society, the dialectical analysis of the change of moral values in the postmodern society, the formation of the moral values of the postmodern society and the perspectives of the approach to it are studied. Also, the essence, scientific and conceptual foundations of the concept of "Postmodern society" are analyzed.

Key words: postmodern society, moral values, dialectics, dialectical analysis, social norms, moral outlook, national and universal values, separatism, fundamentalism, social laws, traditionalism and modernity, comparative analysis, analysis and synthesis, systematic and functional.

Introduction

The initial concepts of postindustrial society were developed by French and American sociologists such as R. Aron and W. Rostow. Scholars and philosophers who analyzed the notion of postindustrial society from socio-philosophical perspectives include D. Bell, T. Kuhn, Z. Brzezinski, and A. Toffler (USA), as well as J. Fourastié and A. Touraine (France), whose works are widely reflected in academic literature. Additionally, other sociologists, economists, political scientists, futurists, and philosophers have contributed their perspectives on postindustrial society. While the aforementioned scholars and thinkers present distinct viewpoints, they also share common scientific approaches. Specifically, postindustrial society is structured in three layers: the first layer pertains to economic activity (agriculture), the second layer to manufacturing, and the third layer to services, infrastructure, science, and education.

Literature review and methods

Issues concerning the development of moral and socio-spiritual culture in individuals, their theoretical-methodological foundations, as well as socio-philosophical and historical problems related to moral and spiritual development, have been studied by scholars such as J. Anderson, S. Anisimov, G. Belov, M. Weber, I. Ilyin, V. Konev, Y. Borev, L. Gumilev, A. Guseynov, V. Lektorsky, I. Ilinsky, M. Kagan, S. Agzamkhodjayeva, J. Tulenov, I. Imonmazarov,

I. Jabborov, Y. Jumaboyev, E. Yusupov, S. Shermukhamedov, Kh. Shaykhova, Mahmud Sattor, A. Jalolov, S. Otamuratov, A. Sharipov, J. Yakhshilikov, N. Mukhammadiyev, A. Erkayev, O. Gaybullayev, I. Arzimatova, and D. Normatova.

Results and discussion

In postindustrial society, significant attention is given to the role and influence of universities. In earlier societies—such as agrarian societies—the church and military were highly valued, while in industrial societies, corporations took precedence. The American sociologist and neoconservative Daniel Bell analyzed the theory of postindustrial society from an antagonistic perspective, categorizing it into three types and outlining its development in three stages: pre-industrial, industrial, and postindustrial. His contemporary, Alvin Toffler, elaborated on this concept through his "Third Wave" theory, presenting detailed scholarly and popular perspectives on this societal model.

According to Toffler, the first wave of societal transformation was marked by land as the primary source of wealth, with agriculture as the dominant activity. The second wave emphasized manufacturing, where corporations played a central role. The third wave is characterized by the widespread adoption of automation, electronics, computerization, the development of jet aircraft, and specialized pharmaceuticals. Unlike J. Fourastié and Touraine, who approached postindustrial society from a radical (European) perspective, Toffler shaped his theory within a liberal framework.

In Toffler's first wave theory, mass society was defined by equivalent technological processes, while the second wave prioritized industrialization. The third wave, however, is distinguished by transformations in economic, social, scientific, and communication structures. Unlike pessimistic scholars who view scientific and technological progress negatively, Toffler advocates for harmonizing this progress with humanistic-ethical values. In this regard, he emphasizes "soft technology," "ecologism," and the "spiritual value of humanism and culture."

Toffler argues that the third wave fundamentally alters social lifestyles, prioritizing individual needs. This shift enhances cognitive abilities, fostering creativity and ultimately cultivating positive moral qualities such as courage, prudence, entrepreneurship, and initiative. As a non-dogmatic sociologist and philosopher—more of a skilled futurist and publicist—Toffler predicted the strategic development mechanisms of the information society. By comparatively analyzing the second and third waves, he identified sharp contrasts in their transformations. While the second wave prioritized wealth and mass

production, the third wave opens vast opportunities for knowledge and creativity. Toffler asserts that the third wave holds far greater and more complex significance than the second, as its intricate processes encompass global and interrelated conflicts.

Through Toffler's framework, we can better understand contemporary political and economic dynamics. However, it should be noted that some of his arguments and ideas have faced criticism from sociologists, cultural theorists, technologists, psychologists, politicians, and philosophers.

In one of the critical approaches, it is noted that his views on satisfying personal needs are grounded in egoism. Overall, Alvin Toffler is considered a renowned scholar and philosopher who captivated the global public with works such as *Future Shock* (1970), *Encounter with the Future*, *The Cultured Consumer* (1973), *The Eco-Spasm Report* (1975), *The Third Wave* (1980), *Previews and Premises* (1985), *The Adaptive Corporation* (1985), *Power Shift* (1990), and others. Later, Toffler and his wife Heidi Toffler jointly published *War and Anti-War*. His scholarly activity is the result of the experience and expertise he accumulated during his life and career.

Alvin Toffler was born in New York City, United States, on October 4, 1928. He graduated from New York University in 1949 and worked as associate editor at *Fortune* magazine from 1959 to 1961. Between 1965 and 1967, he served as a professor at the New School for Social Research, which is affiliated with Cornell University. Currently, Toffler is a member of the Institute for International Studies. His book *Future Shock* brought him worldwide recognition as a distinguished author and consultant. *The Third Wave* is widely regarded as an essential source for understanding global transformations.

The core essence of Toffler's socio-philosophical ideas lies in the assertion that modern technical and technological progress on a global scale has given rise to serious challenges for humanity, and that overcoming these issues must become humanity's foremost noble goal. These challenges include environmental pollution, depletion of natural resources, the threat of nuclear war, clashes of geopolitical interests, hegemonic policies, and other related problems. He emphasizes that in order to solve or prevent such problems, it is vital to effectively apply the moral ideals that have developed and evolved over the course of social and historical progress. Implementing these ideals clearly and promptly into practical life is of urgent importance today. According to Toffler, if humanity remains indifferent to these issues, the collapse of global

civilization will be inevitable. He asserts that the essence and development trajectory of civilization are determined by how well it is structured.

Addressing current civilizational shifts in *The Third Wave*, Toffler makes the following observation:

“In the coming shifts and tumultuous transformations, the true representatives of industrial society—accustomed to pre-established norms—may very well experience the fate of feudal lords from the past. Some will persist, others will find themselves helpless and marginalized—reduced to relics of a bygone nobility. Yet some—those with intelligence and the ability to adapt—will radically transform and become the leaders of the Third Wave.

Tomorrow, when the Third Wave becomes dominant, to understand who will shape the future, we must first understand who is shaping it today.”

Toffler analyzes every social change as a “wave of transformation” and elaborates on the principles, successes, and shortcomings of what he terms the *Second Wave*. He states:

“...we can identify a system composed of six guiding principles. In a sense, we might even call it a ‘program’. This program is implemented to varying degrees across all countries affected by the Second Wave. These six principles—standardization, specialization, synchronization, concentration, maximization, and centralization—can be applied equally to both capitalist and socialist branches of industrial society, as they both emerge inevitably from the separation between production and consumption. Additionally, the increasing significance of the market has facilitated their development.”

He further explains that these principles, reinforcing one another, inevitably lead to the growth of bureaucracy. They have given rise to the largest, most impersonal, and most powerful bureaucratic organizations the world has ever seen—institutions that force people to wander in a world reminiscent of Franz Kafka’s shadowy dominion. If today we feel oppressed and victimized by these principles, we can trace the source of our difficulties. This search leads us to a hidden code embedded within the Second Wave civilization.

Toffler argues for the necessity of transforming these principles, which he describes as the core elements shaping the Second Wave:

“These six principles serve as the explicit blueprint of Second Wave civilization. Today, each of these core principles is under intense assault from the forces of the Third Wave.”

Conclusion. Indeed, there remain true adherents of the Second Wave who continue to apply these principles in business, banking, labor relations,

governance, education, and mass media. The rise of a new civilization challenges all the entrenched interests of the old one. Toffler strives to demonstrate in his views that social development must be implemented on the basis of principles formed during the course of historical and social evolution. He argues that:

“Every civilization has its own hidden code—akin to a unified plan—comprising a system of principles that manifest across all spheres of life. With the spread of industrialism across the planet, its unique internal logic becomes visible. This code consists of six interrelated principles that determine the behavior of millions of individuals.”

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